

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Zheng, M., Zhu, J. (2024). Telling Local Stories: Problems and Paths of Promoting Haining's "Chao Culture" in the Context of Culture and Tourism Integration. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 7(2), 56-62.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.07.02.487

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but are not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Telling Local Stories: Problems and Paths of Promoting Haining's "Chao Culture" in the Context of Culture and Tourism Integration

Minmin Zheng¹, Jiali Zhu²

^{1,2} Zhejiang University of Finance and Economics Dongfang College, Haining 314408, China

Abstract

In the context of the deep integration of culture and tourism, it is urgent to systematically analyze and promote Haining's unique "Chao culture." Through investigation and analysis, it is found that the development of Haining's "Chao culture" faces a number of problems, such as the lack of authenticity of the content, insufficient publicity, unclear target positioning, and irrational allocation of resources. Based on this, three promotion paths are proposed: building a cultural tourism industry chain for large-scale ancient towns, exploring the "Internet +" ancient town model, and building an ecotourism demonstration area with the synergy of multi-party subjects. Through this, we hope to promote the deep integration of Haining Chao culture and tourism, realize the sustainable development of local tourism, and contribute thoughts and solutions to the dissemination and protection of local culture.

Keywords: Cultural Tourism Integration, Chao Culture, Problem Analysis, Path Exploration

1. Introduction

The 2020 Work Points of the Department of Culture and Tourism of Zhejiang Province emphasize the strengthening of the core of the "8-8 Strategy", which aims to further deepen the close integration between the culture and tourism sectors. In order to achieve this vision, Haining City has tapped into and inherited its unique "Chao Culture," which in turn has supported the continued growth of the local tourism industry and the socio-economy. Haining City is located on the Hangjiahu Plain in Zhejiang Province, which is rich in land resources and deep in history and culture. In particular, the "Chao culture," as a unique asset of this land, has gradually become a core driving force for the development of the local tourism industry.

Under the background of the current social and economic development, the culture and tourism industry is constantly rising, and the integration of culture and tourism has gradually become the inevitable development trend of the tourism industry. In recent years, research on the dissemination path of Haining's "Chao culture" and successful experiences at home and abroad have provided us with valuable references and inspirations. Wu Jialin (2022) analyzed the realization path of tourism development in Yanguan Town, Haining City, under the background of culture and tourism integration, and concluded that it should be based on regional cultural

characteristics, fully explore the potential of Haining's "Chao culture," focus on the innovation of culture and tourism products, enhance the attractiveness of tourist attractions, integrate the existing infrastructure and tourism resources, improve the quality of tourism, and meet the needs of tourists. To meet the needs of tourists. Liu Yihong (2022) researched from the perspective of visual image of the city logo, and put forward the design scheme of Haining city logo with the theme of "Chao culture", which provided new ideas for the promotion of Haining city image (Wu, 2022).

In the current social background of the deep integration of culture and tourism industry, the deep excavation of local cultural resources and the continuous inheritance of traditions have become particularly important. Haining City has learned from Wuzhen's successful practice of integrating culture and tourism, and combined it with cutting-edge technologies such as "Internet+" to continuously research and innovate cultural communication means, with the goal of strengthening the global dissemination of "Chao culture." Haining's "Chao culture" has received solid support from government policies, laying a solid foundation for its development. The "Implementation Recommendations on Promoting High-Quality Integration and Development of Culture and Tourism" emphasizes the importance of integrating culture and tourism standards in the Yangtze River Delta region, while the "Comprehensive Evaluation Approach for the Development of Culture and Tourism Integration IPs in Zhejiang Province" proposes fostering more integrated IPs for culture and tourism. The implementation of these policies provides a clear direction and solid support for the further development and promotion of "Chao Culture" in Haining City.

Under the current trend of integration of cultural tourism and tourism industry, it is particularly important to promote tourism-related promotional activities. In order to deepen the promotion of "Chao Culture," Haining City has implemented innovative strategies and proactive exploration in the tourism market, making full use of cutting-edge media and network technology and improving its competitiveness in the market through various ways and means. As a key path for the integration of culture and tourism, Haining City has carried out in-depth research and promotion of "Chao culture," integrating it into tourism products and services to provide tourists with unique cultural experiences, thus enhancing its tourism value and market competitiveness. Jin Sanmin (1995) conducted an in-depth study on the development of tourism resources in Yanguan, a tide-watching resort, and concluded that the development of tide culture tourism resources should seize unique attractions such as the tide bridge and the Yanguan tide-watching building, as well as various kinds of folk cultural activities (Liu, 2022). In addition, the development of tourism facilities and services centered on regional characteristics will give tourists more diversified feelings ^[4]. Wuzhen, as a successful example of international cultural tourism development, has rich historical and cultural connotations and unique regional characteristics (Zhou Xuerui et al., 2021).

Taking Wuzhen Theatre Festival as a case study, Yi Xiuzhu and Fan Hong (2023) analyze the branding strategy for shaping national image in international cultural tourism, and argue that the success of Wuzhen Theatre Festival is due to the effective integration of cultural and tourism resources, highlighting historical and cultural individuality, avoiding over-commercialization, and establishing a "scenario of cultural and tourism fusion and a modality of social welfare" (Yi & Fan, 2023). By exploring the symbiotic mechanism of tourism characteristic towns, Wu Wenwen (2020) proposed that in the integration of regional culture and tourism resources, the roles of the government, commercial organizations, and the general public should be brought into play in order to deeply implement the strategy of culture-tourism integration (Wu, 2020). Susan (2021) reveals a successful case of cultural and tourism integration by deconstructing Wuzhen Theater Festival, which provides a reference for other regions (Susan, 2021).

Through an in-depth analysis of Haining City's efforts and strategies in integrating culture and tourism, we can not only summarize its successful experience in this field, but also identify the current bottlenecks and shortcomings, so as to provide strong scientific support for future planning. Haining City has achieved remarkable results in promoting "Chao culture" and the integration of culture and tourism, but more exploration and innovation are needed in order to more deeply explore and inherit the unique culture of the city and to further promote the overall development of tourism and economy and society. Haining City is not only of far-reaching significance, it also provides valuable practical experience and inspiration for other regions to work together to promote the development and popularization of local culture in China.

2. Haining "Chao culture" cultural tourism promotion existing problems

2.1. Lack of authenticity of content

Some inherent lack of authenticity can be clearly observed in the promotion and growth of the cultural and tourism industries in Haining City. This is mainly due to the fact that part of the tourism industry fails to fully explore and inherit the original cultural landscape, or explore and pass on the local culture in depth, and occasionally draws on cultural factors that are not directly related to the local cultural context. Such behavior may damage the unique charm of Chao culture, thus reducing the experience of tourists (Zhou, Wang, & Xin, 2021). Some actual projects, such as the resort attractions developed in Yanguan Town, have neglected to pay attention to the authenticity of Chao culture, resulting in tourists not being able to truly experience the original charm brought by Chao culture during their visits. Similarly, when implementing Chao culture activities, the specific content of certain activities has misinterpreted the true connotation of the regional culture, overly pursuing commercial gains while ignoring the importance of cultural traditions and presentation, and this behavior tends to diminish the attraction brought by Chao culture.

In the face of this matter, we should think deeply about how to cherish the authenticity of Chao culture more in the progress of Haining City's cultural tourism industry. In the process of planning tourist attractions, first of all, we should attach great importance to the guardianship and deep excavation of the past culture to ensure that the cultural heritage maintains its original and beautiful appearance. Furthermore, when carrying out cultural activities, it is important to ensure that the activities are harmoniously integrated with the local culture, avoiding excessive commercial operations or the inclusion of irrelevant elements. With this set of strategic tools, tourists will be able to experience the unique flavor of tidal culture in a more in-depth manner, which will further enhance the attractiveness to the cultural and tourism industries. Moreover, adhering to and passing on this concept will help Haining City build stronger competitiveness in the growth of its cultural and tourism industry.

2.2. Insufficient publicity

In the case of Haining City's Chao culture in the promotion of cultural tourism, the challenge of lack of promotional activities was indeed encountered. In the early days, the degree of diversification of the various publicity strategies was not prominent, and most of them were limited to traditional methods such as paper media and outdoor advertisements, which to a certain extent limited the coverage and depth of their promotion. The purpose of publicity was not clear enough, which made it difficult for certain publicity content to precisely serve the target group. A combination of many factors has led to the lagging growth of Haining Chao culture in terms of public awareness and influence.

To truly address the shortcomings in the promotion of Chao culture, it is first necessary for Haining City to invest more resources in this cultural field and adopt a variety of methods to increase the public awareness of Chao culture and its scope of influence. The advantages of network technology and new media platforms can be utilized to expand the scope of information dissemination, and the combination of online and offline is emphasized to ensure the comprehensiveness and accuracy of the dissemination process. Next, the promotion strategy should emphasize the unique features of Chao culture, its regional characteristics and contemporary flavor, and closely integrate it with the preferences and needs of tourists, so as to attract more audiences to participate in it.

In addition to this, it is committed to deepening cooperative relationships with cultural and tourism brands in other cities, drawing on their successful models and marketing strategies, with the aim of enhancing the brand promotion value of Haining's tide culture. Haining City can refer to the experience of Wuzhen Drama Festival and other cultural and tourism events in its publicity and promotion, presenting the deep charm of tide in its innovative and unique way. By optimizing and improving the content and methods of publicity, Haining City aims to further increase the impact of Chao culture and further promote the growth of the cultural tourism industry, making meaningful contributions to the inheritance and promotion of Chao culture.

2.3. Unclear targeting

In Haining City's promotional activities for Chao culture and cultural tourism, the challenge of ambiguous orientation and positioning was indeed encountered. Many cultural and tourism products are insufficient in terms of lack of novelty and uniqueness, thus leading to ambiguity in their market orientation. On the one hand, the fundamental significance and unique characteristics of the Chao culture have not been adequately demonstrated and widely shared because of the public's in-depth understanding of the Chao culture; on the other hand, the promotional activities have failed to accurately convey to potential tourists the unique attraction of the Chao culture due to the insufficient relevance of the selection of the target market and the dissemination of information.

To address the core issue of cultural tourism promotion, the first task is to dig deeper into the basic value of Chao culture and extract distinctive elements and features from it to give it a higher level of charm. Secondly, in order to increase the attention of a specific market, design marketing strategies that are more innovative and unique to Chao culture products. When studying Chao culture in depth, we will find its special connotation and values that are significantly different from other cultures. This makes it show its unique competitive advantage in the fiercely competitive cultural tourism market.

In the promotional activities, the unique charm of the Chao culture needs to be more precisely conveyed to the intended visitors. For example, a variety of promotional programs targeting various age groups and specific interest groups can be implemented to enhance the awareness and market impact of Chao culture in various industries. By establishing a clear marketing strategy, Haining City is expected to more effectively promote the growth of the cultural tourism industry and fully present the unique appeal of Chao culture to attract more tourists to experience it for themselves.

2.4. Unreasonable allocation of resources

In the process of promoting Chao culture and cultural tourism, Haining City does face the problem of uneven allocation of resources. Obviously, we can divide it into two aspects: the unbalanced development of tourism resources and the incomplete infrastructure. Places with profound tidal culture significance like the Yanguan Ancient City and Haining's tide-watching resorts may not have received enough attention and capital investment, which may have resulted in their cultural value and attractiveness not being adequately reflected. In addition, due to problems with infrastructure such as transportation, tour guide services and service equipment, all of these factors negatively affect the quality of the visitor experience and limit in-depth exploration of Chao culture and cultural activities.

In order to effectively address this set of challenges, the Haining municipal government and related departments should increase their financial investment in tourism and Chaozhou cultural resources in order to achieve a more balanced distribution of resources. Commit to providing tourists with richer and more diversified sightseeing options and cultural experiences through scientific and rational planning of tourism resources, as well as in-depth excavation and application of existing cultural resources. From a different perspective, the direction of diversification of Chao cultural tourism products is further spawned by strengthening and optimizing infrastructure development to enhance visitor experience. Considering the above factors, Haining City has decided to further reorganize its resource allocation to provide tourists with a higher-quality tourism experience, which will enhance the competitiveness and attractiveness of Chao culture in the field of cultural tourism, thus promoting its sustainable and prosperous development.

3. Haining "Chao culture" cultural tourism promotion Path exploration

3.1. Building a cultural and tourism industry chain for large-scale ancient towns

In the process of integrating resources and comprehensive development, Haining City has drawn on the successful experience of Wuzhen, and is committed to creating a large-scale ancient town cultural tourism industry chain that incorporates elements of Chao culture. By integrating the resources of various scenic spots in the region, it has

formed a cluster of characteristic towns with Yanguan Town as the core, and created a comprehensive modern town integrating leisure and entertainment, catering and shopping. Firstly, Haining City has carried out all-round planning and design for key tourist attractions such as Yanguan Ancient Town and Haining Tide Watching Resort, implemented unified property rights and management and protection measures, and especially focused on the maintenance and restoration work of the original appearance of the ancient town. Secondly, traditional residential buildings and landscape resources have been integrated on the basis of digital technology. Following the principle of "protection first, repairing the old as the old, and preserving its authenticity," the authenticity and historical meaning of the Chaozhou culture have been demonstrated.

In order to create more jobs and increase the economic income of local residents, some local residents are hired to work in the tertiary sector. We are committed to promoting the development of tourism industries such as handicrafts with regional characteristics, gourmet foods, and folk cultural activities, with the aim of attracting more tourists to come and experience them. On this basis, we combine tourism with other related industries to form a diversified economic model. Taking Yanguan Ancient City as the object of study, its Yanguan intangible cultural heritage projects and tide-watching cultural activities are centered on tide culture, providing tourists with travel experiences rich in local characteristics, and thus shaping the unique cultural tourism industry chain of Haining City.

In order to prevent over-exploitation and commercialization, it is important to pay attention to the original characteristics of the Chao culture in Haining and to increase the economic returns of the cultural tourism industry in Haining through targeted publicity and promotional activities to raise tourists' awareness of the Chao culture. At the same time, the government also needs to increase support for the cultural industry and encourage enterprises to actively invest in the excavation and protection of Chao culture elements. For example, by organizing all kinds of tourism activities, festival celebrations and marketing promotions focusing on Chao culture, the Chao culture in Haining City will show its unique charm and traditional charms, which not only attracts more tourists to participate, but also further promotes the continued prosperity and progress of the cultural tourism industry.

3.2. Explore the "Internet +" ancient town model

Haining City is actively seeking to drive innovation, combining the cutting-edge technology of "Internet+" and traditional cultural resources towards modernization, with the goal of injecting new vitality into the future development of Haining's Chao cultural tourism.

Haining City has been actively utilizing online resources, official government websites and other diverse social platforms in the mass media and emerging information media to carry out a wide range of publicity and marketing activities. A new website for the word "sea" has been set up through Internet technology and promoted as one of the important contents. Through the dissemination of cultural stories related to tides, it can show the unique characteristics of the region's cultural activities, thus increasing the visibility of Haining's tide culture in the society. We also interact with the outside world through the Internet. We provide tourists with a wide range of information such as travel guides, daily activity schedules and food suggestions for places such as Yanguan City Wall and Haining Tidewater Watching Resort to ensure that tourists are able to obtain the latest information and services for their travels in a timely manner.

Through the combination of digital payment and online ticketing, the traditional Chao culture tourism experience in Haining City will become more convenient. On this basis, the publicity and promotion of the scenic spots as well as the cooperation with third parties are used to increase the popularity and reputation of the scenic spots. Through multifunctional services such as online ticketing and accommodation booking, travelers are provided with a more convenient travel experience. In order to provide visitors with more convenient and humanized access to tourism information, the platform launched a virtual tour guide application called "Haining Tourism," which provides immersive and real-time guided tours.

Finally, the selection of innovative strategies as a driving force has significantly advanced the development of the tidal culture tourism chain. By integrating cultural heritage materials such as intangible cultural heritage projects

and tide viewing activities in Yan Guan, Haining City, and utilizing advanced digital technologies such as virtual reality and augmented reality, an innovative interactive experience is provided for tourists. It is also hoped to promote the sustainable development of the local tourism industry by utilizing the unique spirituality and aesthetic appeal of tidal culture. Starting from the deeper meaning of culture and with the core goal of serving the public, we hope to push the Chao culture tourism in Haining City to a new peak and find more innovative directions for the future development strategy of the ancient town.

3.3. Multi-party synergy to build an ecotourism demonstration area

With the growing global interest in and love for ecotourism, Haining City decided to create a model that integrates industry, education and research, with the core objective of creating an ecotourism demonstration area that showcases the region's unique ecology, Chao culture and folk traditions.

By maintaining close cooperation with major higher education and research institutions, it aims to deeply explore the rich tourism and cultural heritage of Haining City. Through synergistic innovation between universities, research institutions, museums and other relevant units, traditional skills are organically combined with modern technology to revitalize them, thus promoting local tourism. For example, tourist attractions like the Yanguan Ancient City and tide-watching resorts, as well as intangible cultural heritage items, are undergoing a process of development and preservation. In this process, we hope to promote the development of cultural industries in the region through the strengths of universities and research institutions. By taking advantage of the strong scientific research capabilities and specialized features of universities and research centers, we have conducted in-depth research on the ecological environment, geographic features, and history and culture of Haining City, with the aim of more accurately presenting the natural beauty and humanistic values of the region.

Subsequently, the guiding role of local governments has promoted deeper integration and innovative development with related industries. In this paper, we will take Haining as an example to study and analyze its tourism and economic synergy development and put forward some constructive suggestions. Our goal is to establish a co-growth strategy in a number of fields, including tourism, agriculture, handicrafts and local folk culture. By establishing a more complete cultural industry chain, the tourism industry of Haining City has been better enhanced and the regional economy has been further promoted. For example, diversified activities such as folk performances and handicrafts have been introduced in tourist attractions like the Tide Watching Resort and Yanguan Ancient City, which provide tourists with an opportunity to deeply experience the unique cultural atmosphere of Haining City.

Finally, the concerted efforts of many parties to create the Haining "Chao Culture" Ecotourism Demonstration Zone require the joint efforts of the government, market, science and technology, education and other aspects. Through policy guidance, market response, technological innovation and academic support, we can promote the sustainable development of Haining's culture and tourism industry, provide tourists with a richer and more distinctive tourism experience, and jointly promote the vigorous development of Haining's culture and tourism industry.

Declaration of Competing Interest: The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to acknowledge all the team members.

Author Statement: All authors agree with submission of this version.

Availability of data: The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Funding: This work was supported by Innovation and Entrepreneurship Training Programme for College Students of Zhejiang University of Finance and Economics Dongfang College; National Level; Project No.: 202313294010; Project Name: Telling Local Stories: Exploring the Promotion Path of Haining's "Chao Culture" under the Background of Culture and Tourism Integration.

References

- Wu, J. (2022). Realization Path of Tourism Development of Yanguan Town, Haining City under the Background of Culture and Tourism Integration [Doctoral dissertation, Shanghai Academy of Social Sciences].
- Liu, Y. (2022). Research on Visual Image of Haining City Logo Based on "Chao Culture." *Culture Industry*, 2022(13), 155-158.
- "Big data +" mode hand in hand "manufacturing industry +" - Wuzhen big data industrial park area construction "roadmap "Roadmap" for the construction of Wuzhen Big Data Industrial Park. (2020). *Informatization Construction*, 2020(06), 40-41.
- Jin, S. (1995). Research on the development of tourism resources in Yanguan, a tide-watching resort. *Journal of Shaanxi Normal University (Natural Science Edition)*, 1995(S1), 157-160.
- Yi, X., & Fan, H. (2023). Branding Strategy of Characteristic Towns to Shape National Image in International Cultural Tourism--Taking Wuzhen Drama Festival as an Example. *Journal of Central South University for Nationalities (Humanities and Social Sciences Edition)*, 2023, 43(06), 71-81+183-184.
- Wu, W. (2020). Research on the symbiosis mechanism of tourism characteristic town [Doctoral dissertation, Shanghai Normal University].
- Susan. (2021). Deconstructing the Wuzhen Theater Festival-a successful example of cultural and tourism integration. *Sichuan Drama*, 2021(11), 42-45.
- Zhou, X., Wang, X., & Xin, T. (2021). Analysis of key factors for the success of cultural and tourism feature towns in urban suburbs. *Modern Business*, 2021(08), 130-132.